

Ephydrid flies [Diptera: Ephydridae] of rice in the Philippines

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Rice whorl maggot (RWM) *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino is the only ephydrid rice pest recorded in the Philippines. RWM damages rice leaves at early vegetative stage all year in rainfed and irrigated lowlands. We collected ephydrid flies by D-Vac suction machine, sweep net, and mylar plastic cone traps from 1977 to 1980 from different rice cultures in the Philippines. Cone traps were placed open-end-down over flies on plants. The mylar plastic cone trap caught more flies than D-Vac or sweep nets. Plants with leaf damage were dissected for larvae and pupae, which were reared to adulthood on leaf sections kept on moist filter paper in plastic dishes. The ephydrid fauna of Philippine rice fields includes 10 genera and 18 species. Of the species, 12 are phytophagous, 5 are scavengers, and 1 is a predator (see table), as determined by P.J. Clausen, Entomology Department, University of Minnesota, USA, except *Ochthera*.

Eleven species in seven genera are new Philippine records. Three species live in uplands, 11 in rainfed lowlands, 13 in irrigated areas, and 8 in irrigated rice terraces. All but *Actocetor beckeri* de Meijere were recorded in lowland and irrigated areas, which suggests that ephydrid flies prefer aquatic or semi-aquatic environments. The Banawe rice terraces, which have high elevation and low temperature, and produce two rice crops a year, had almost the same species as the rainfed and irrigated lowlands. Twelve species belonging to the subfamilies Psilopinae and Notiphilinae (except *B. longipes*) emerged from the plants with whorl maggot leaf damage and were considered phytophagous (see table and figure). *Hydrellia*, *Notiphila*, *Paralima*, and *Psilopa* are phytophagous genera from the rainfed and irrigated lowlands. *Brachydeutera* was found in the terraces.

Hydrellia philippina was most common in irrigated lowlands, *Psilopa* spp. in rainfed lowlands, and *H. griseola* in terraces. This fly is commonly called rice leaf miner and has limited distribution in temperate zones including the USA, Europe, North Africa, Japan, and Korea. *Notiphila laligenis* and *N. similis* were numerous on emergent vegetation and, usually laid eggs on the stem of the perennial fern *Marsilea minuta* L. The eggs were an alternate host of the stem borer egg parasite *Trichogramma*. *Discomyza maculipennis* (Weidemann) is a scavenger and emerged from dead *Lymnaea* and *Pila* snails. Ephydrid flies are generally beneficial and provide food for spiders, toads and frogs, and wildlife that inhabit rice fields and marshes.

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Species	Rice culture ^a			
	Upland	Rainfed lowland	Irrigated lowland	Irrigated rice terraces
1. <i>Actocetor beckeri</i> de Meijere ^{be}	+	-	-	-
2. <i>Brachydeutera longipes</i> Hendel ^c	+	-	+	+f
3. <i>Discomyza maculipennis</i> (Weidemann) ^{be}	-	+	-	-
4. <i>Hydrellia griseola</i> (Fallen) ^{ce}	-	-	+f	+f
5. <i>Hydrellia philippina</i> Ferino ^c	-	+f	+f	-
6. <i>Notiphila latigenis</i> Hendel ^{ce}	-	+	+f	+f
7. <i>Notiphila similis</i> de Meijere ^{ce}	-	+f	+	-
8. <i>Notiphila spinosa</i> Cresson ^c	-	+	+f	+
9. <i>Ochthera</i> sp. ^d	-	+	+	+
10. <i>Paralimna lineata</i> de Meijere ^c	+	+f	-	-
11. <i>Paralimna picta</i> Kertesz ^c	-	+f	-	+f
12. <i>Polytrichophora brunneifrons</i> (de Meijere) ^{be}	-	+	+	+
13. <i>Psilopa flavimana</i> Hendel ^{ce}	-	-	+f	-
14. <i>Psilopa pollinosa</i> (Kertesz) ^{ce}	-	+f	+f	-
15. <i>Psilopa rufipes</i> Hendel ^c	-	-	+f	+
16. <i>Psilopa sorella</i> Becker ^{ce}	-	+f	-	-
17. <i>Scatella callisicosta</i> Bezzi ^{be}	-	-	+	-
18. <i>Scatella</i> sp. ^{be}	-	-	+	-
Total	3	11	13	8

^a+ = collected, - = not collected. ^bScavenger. ^cPhytophagous. ^dPredator. ^eNew Philippine record. ^fReared from plants with leaf damage.

